

Far Infrared Studies of Some Organotin Adducts

K. L. Jaura and K. K. Sharma

In continuation of our earlier communications^{1,2}, where formation of adducts of Ph_3SnCl , Ph_2SnCl_2 and $n\text{PrSnCl}_3$ with amines has been reported, the assignments for frequencies of these adducts in the region below 400 cm^{-1} have been made (Tables I, II and III).

The infrared studies have been carried out as KBr discs in case of adducts of Ph_2SnCl_2 and $n\text{PrSnCl}_3$ and as nujol mulls in caesium bromide plates in case of adducts of Ph_3SnCl .

The frequencies corresponding to Sn-Ph stretching vibrations in organotin chlorides are observed³ in the vicinity of 250 cm^{-1} and those of Sn-Cl stretching vibrations around 360 cm^{-1} . On the formation of adducts the Sn-Ph stretching frequencies are not affected, whereas those of Sn-Cl are lowered. Due to proximity of these Sn-Ph and Sn-Cl frequencies in the adduct molecules some mixing up of the both cannot be ruled out. Even then their use for structural determinations cannot be minimised.

In the adducts with 1 : 2 stoichiometry tin is evidently in octahedral environments. But in the 1 : 4 adducts also tin has been shown to be hexa-coordinated and only two of the four ligands are known to coordinate⁴.

TABLE I

(Sn—Cl) frequencies (cm^{-1})

$n\text{PrSnCl}_3$	360 s, 350 sh, 310 s, 305 sh
$n\text{PrSnCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Pyridine}$	310–300 m. br., 280 m, 260 m
$n\text{PrSnCl}_3 \cdot 2\beta\text{-picoline}$	318 s, 285 w, 260 s.br
$n\text{PrSnCl}_3 \cdot 4\gamma\text{-picoline}$	325 w.br, 280–260 m.br
$n\text{PrSnCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{ isoquinoline}$	358–345 w.br, ? 260 w.
$n\text{PrSnCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{ Piperidine}$	340 m, ? 290 w, 270 m.
$n\text{PrSnCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{ morpholine}$	275 m, 270 w.
$n\text{PrSnCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{ aniline}$	350 s, ? 325 w, 300 m.
$n\text{PrSnCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{ benzylamine}$	370 w, ? 350 m, ? 310 m.

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2. K. L. Jaura, Kuldip Chander and K. K. Sharma, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1970, **376**, 303.
3. R. C. Poller and D. L. B. Toley, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 1578.
4. K. L. Jaura and K. K. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press).

The multiplicity of frequencies in Sn-Cl region (Table I) indicates that two of the chlorines may be present in the cis positions leading subsequently to two types of structural arrangements as (A) or (B) depending upon the size of the ligands attached and represented as :

In (A) the ligands are comparatively bulky.

TABLE II

	$\nu(\text{Sn-Cl}) \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\nu(\text{Sn-Ph}) \text{ cm}^{-1}$		Unassigned frequencies
		A sym.	Sym.	
Ph_3SnCl^a	340-338s,	277-272s	231s	—
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl} \cdot 2 \text{ pyridine}$	305w, 225s	275s, 270s	245s	225w, 220w, 210w
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl} \cdot 2\beta\text{-picoline}$	300w, 255(s,br)	275s	240s	225w, 220w, 210w, 205w
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl} \cdot 2\gamma\text{-picoline}$	305w, 255-250(s,br)	270s	240s	225w, 220w, 215w, 210w
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl} \cdot \text{isoquinoline}$	260s,	280s, 270s	240s	225w, 220w, 215w, 210w
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl} \cdot \text{piperidine}$	300w, 250s	280s	240s	225w, 215m, 210w, 205w
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl} \cdot \text{morpholine}$	305m, 255-250(s,br.)	275s	240s	220m, 210w, 205w
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl} \cdot x\text{-aniline}$	305m, 255s	270s	240s	225w, 220m, 210w, 205w
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl} \cdot \text{benzylamine}$	300w, 255-250(s,br.)	?	240s	225w, 215w, 210w

On the basis of infrared frequencies, on similar lines, in Sn-Cl region (Table III) subject to the size of the ligands, two possible structures can be assigned to the adducts of Ph_2SnCl_2 as:

With ligands comparatively smaller in size, the phenyl groups would tend to occupy trans positions and yield structure (C). But in case the ligands are bulky, the phenyl groups would be forced into the cis positions with structure (D). By other methods⁵ also it has been established that in these adducts structure (C) is mostly encountered, corresponding morpholine adduct where phenyl groups may occupy cis positions, being the only exception with the possibility of structure (D).

5. B. A. Goodman, N. N. Greenwood, K. L. Jaura and K. K. Sharma, *J. Chem. Soc.* (in press).

TABLE III

	$\nu(\text{Sn-Cl}) \text{ cm}^{-1}$		$\nu(\text{Sn-Ph}) \text{ cm}^{-1}$
	Asym.	Sym.	Asym.
$\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2^3$	364 s	356 s, sh 350 s	279-274 s, sh
$\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 4$ pyridine	—	305 m	280 m
$\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 4$ α -picoline	325 s	300 m	280 m
$\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 4$ β -picoline	330 w	305 w	280 w
$\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 4$ γ -picoline	335 w	390 s	—
$\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2$ isoquinoline	320 w	—	275 m
$\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 4$ piperidine	310 m	—	—
$\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 4$ morpholine	315 s	—	260 w
$\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2$ aniline	—	300 s	—
$\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2$ benzylamine	315 s	300 w	—

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Department of Chemistry,
Panjab University,
Chandigarh-14.

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